

D4.1. Guidelines on cybersecurity civil-defence cooperation

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Authors	ULB
Reviewers	IVSZ & INFOBALT

Abstract

This report summarises the research activities conducted under Task 4.1 of the COcyber project, dedicated to identifying and validating a set of best practices aimed at enhancing cybersecurity cooperation between the civilian and defence sectors across the European Union. As cyber threats increasingly blur the lines between civilian and military targets, establishing structured and effective collaboration models has become essential to building a resilient and united cybersecurity ecosystem.

The objective of Task 4.1 was to uncover **at least 10 transferable best practices** that reflect successful examples of civil-defence cooperation. These practices were selected through a rigorous process involving **desk research, consultations with relevant stakeholders**, and a **validation and rating phase** conducted with subject-matter experts from across Europe.

The practices address a wide range of operational and strategic needs, including real-time threat intelligence sharing, joint training and capacity building, interoperable crisis management, dual-use technology alignment, and coordinated procurement. Each practice is accompanied by a description of its relevance, an assessment of the key factors that enabled its success, and practical guidance for implementation in other contexts.

In addition to identifying what works, the report introduces a framework for evaluating best practices based on a set of **quality criteria and key performance indicators (KPIs)**. This approach ensures not only the relevance and impact of the practices selected but also their potential for replication, scalability, and policy alignment at both national and EU levels.

By delivering a structured collection of validated and actionable practices, accompanied by implementation guidelines, this report **lays the essential groundwork for future activities under Task 4.2 and informs the development of policy recommendations in Deliverable 4.5**, the final phase of the COcyber project. It is intended to serve as a comprehensive reference point for government agencies and regulators, private sector representatives, academic institutions, civil society or industry associations, military-related organisations, as well as cybersecurity professionals and policymakers seeking to strengthen cross-sector coordination and operational cooperation in response to increasingly complex and evolving cyber challenges.

Keywords

Cybersecurity Best Practices, Cybersecurity Collaboration, Civilian Defence Partnership, Civilian-Defence Cooperation, Cross-Sector Collaboration, Critical Infrastructure Protection, Strategic Cyber Partnerships, Joint Cyber Capabilities

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* Deliverable types:

R: document, report (excluding periodic and final reports).

DEM: demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs.

DEC: websites, patent filings, press and media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: software, technical diagrams, etc.

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
ULB	Université Libre de Bruxelles Solvay Brussels School, COcyber partner leading Know-how, good practice sharing, and information transfer activities (WP4).
EU	European Union
MS	Member States
LR	Literature review
CCDCOE	NATO Cooperative Cyber Defence Centre of Excellence
ECYBRIDGE	ECYBRIDGE project
ECSF	European Cybersecurity Skills Framework
SIM3	Security Incident Management Maturity Model
CRRT(s)	Cyber Rapid Response Teams
PESCO	Permanent Structured Cooperation
CSIRT(s)	Computer Security Incident Response Team(s)
CERT(s)	Computer Emergency Response Team(s)
FIRST	Forum of Incident Response and Security Teams
PROGRESS CCMM	Cybersecurity Capability Maturity Model
COBIT	Control Objectives for Information and Related Technologies
NIST CSF	CSF – National Institute of Standards and Technology Cybersecurity Framework
MITRE ATT&CK	Adversarial Tactics, Techniques, and Common Knowledge
IOCTA	Internet Organised Crime Threat Assessment
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
EDA	European Defence Agency
ENISA	European Union Agency for Cybersecurity
NIS2	Directive on Security of Network and Information Systems

1 Introduction

1.1 Synopsis of the need for Guidelines on cybersecurity civil-defence collaboration

The digital landscape of the European Union is facing an unprecedented surge in cyber threats that cut across both civilian and defence sectors. In 2023 alone, reported cyber incidents across the EU rose by more than 20%, with critical infrastructure sectors being among the most frequently targeted—underscoring both the urgency and the shared nature of the challenge.¹ The increasing sophistication, scale, and impact of cyberattacks, ranging from ransomware crippling healthcare systems to state-sponsored intrusions targeting critical defence infrastructure, have highlighted one inescapable reality: cybersecurity can no longer be tackled in silos.

Traditionally, civilian and defence cybersecurity communities have operated along distinct paths. Civilian institutions, such as energy providers, financial institutions, and public administration bodies, prioritise the continuity of essential services, data protection, and regulatory compliance. Meanwhile, defence actors focus on mission assurance, national security systems, and classified communications. Yet the boundary between these domains is now increasingly vulnerable. Shared infrastructures, interconnected supply chains, and the dual-use nature of emerging technologies mean that vulnerabilities in one sphere inevitably ripple into the other. Unlike many existing EU cybersecurity reports, this document goes beyond theoretical analysis by providing a set of practical and transferable best practices. These practices have been systematically validated by experts to ensure their operational relevance, scalability, and potential for replication across diverse national and sectoral contexts.

The COcyber project was designed to respond to this complex challenge by fostering structured cooperation between the civilian and defence cybersecurity communities. As part of this mission, **Task 4.1 focuses on identifying, validating, and promoting a set of best practices** that exemplify successful collaboration across Europe.

These best practices aim to address persistent gaps in coordination, joint response, and knowledge transfer by providing replicable models that bridge the

¹ <https://www.enisa.europa.eu/news/cyber-europe-tests-the-eu-cyber-preparedness-in-the-energy-sector>

two communities. Developed through extensive desk research, stakeholder engagement, and expert validation, **the 11 best practices presented in this report offer actionable approaches to enhance the cooperation between the two cybersecurity communities.** They cover key areas such as real-time intelligence sharing, dual-use technology development, joint training initiatives, governance alignment, and coordinated incident response.

Each practice has been reviewed against a robust set of quality criteria and KPIs to ensure relevance, scalability, and sustainability.

This document serves as a practical guideline designed to support the development of a unified cybersecurity ecosystem. Drawing on validated efforts across Member States, the report provides policymakers, practitioners, and strategists with actionable recommendations and frameworks to build integrated cyber capabilities and foster institutional trust.

Ultimately, the goal of this work is to **contribute to the way for a stronger, more resilient, and more cooperative European cybersecurity posture**—one in which both civilian and defence actors stand shoulder-to-shoulder in facing the threats of today and tomorrow.

1.2 Technical specifications

The **objective** of this study is to identify and validate a set of best practices that can strengthen structured cybersecurity cooperation between civilian and defence sectors across the European Union.

The focus is placed on selecting initiatives that support cross-sector information sharing, joint training programs, integrated crisis response strategies, technology co-development, and other dimensions of practical cooperation. These initiatives are expected to generate tangible real-world impact, such as faster detection of cyber incidents, improved coordination during crises, and more resilient joint responses across civilian and defence domains.

Each best practice is evaluated not only for its effectiveness but also for its scalability, sustainability, and potential for replication across other national and sectoral contexts within the EU.

Ultimately, this task supports the development of Deliverable D4.1, which provides strategic insights and cooperation guidelines to stakeholders from both sectors, contributing to a more secure and cohesive European digital space.

1.1.1. Study questions

To guide the research, the following **central questions** were formulated:

- What types of structured cooperation currently exist between the civilian and defence cybersecurity communities in the EU?
- What characteristics make a cybersecurity cooperation practice “effective,” “scalable,” and “transferable” across different EU Member States?
- What barriers and enablers influence the success of civil-defence collaboration in cybersecurity?
- Which critical gaps remain in the coordination between the two communities, and how can practical examples address them?

These research questions helped ensure a rigorous and policy-relevant approach while maintaining alignment with academic and operational priorities in cybersecurity governance.

1.1.2. Methodology

The methodology for Task 4.1 follows a structured **three-step design process** aimed at **identifying, evaluating, and validating a set of impactful best practices** for enhancing cybersecurity cooperation between the civil-defence sectors in the EU:

1.1.2.1. Step 1 – “Literature review and desk research”

Step 1 is a data collection phase with the primary objective of building a comprehensive “Long List of Practices.” This effort aimed to ensure **wide coverage** of national, European, and non-European initiatives, chosen for their relevance and potential applicability to the European context, encompassing both past and ongoing efforts.

1.1.2.1.1. Step 1.1. Desk Research

The process began with a **broad and systematic collection of candidate practices** through open-source intelligence, desk research, institutional databases, project repositories (e.g., ENISA, EDA, Horizon Europe projects), and internal partner contributions.

ULB team of Researchers reviewed over 600+ sources, including ENISA and EDA reports, EU cybersecurity frameworks, NATO publications, academic literature, and policy analyses.

Each source was logged in a repository of “Candidate Practice”, and then coded and classified by sector, origin, typology, and thematic alignment (e.g., dual-use innovation, procurement collaboration, or joint incident response). This initial mapping helped identify the **recurring domains of cooperation** (e.g., joint incident response, procurement, dual-use innovation, crisis coordination) and shaped the dimensions to be explored further.

1.1.2.1.2. Step 1.2. Open Call for best practices

On top of desk research and literature review, a **structured digital call for best practices** was launched, using a digital form disseminated to stakeholders across the EU civil-defence cybersecurity ecosystem.

The team reached out to several cybersecurity experts, and 12 of them submitted practices using a predefined form, detailing implementation strategies, governance models, impacts, and replication potential. This ensured comparability of input and enabled later classification.

1.1.2.1.3. Step 1.3. Stakeholder consultations

The repository of best practices built through Step 1.1 and Step 1.2 was then further enriched through **targeted stakeholder consultations**.

ULB Team conducted targeted outreach with a diverse group of experts, including cybersecurity and digital resilience specialists from national and EU-level industry actors (e.g., NRD Cyber Security, CYEN, EOS), academic researchers in cyber-physical systems, digital policy, and distributed computing (e.g., University, National Technical University of Athens, National University of Public Service), public-sector and financial cybersecurity professionals (e.g., Central Bank of Hungary, CEA France), and policy advisors engaged in EU digital governance and critical infrastructure protection (e.g., The Lisbon Council, Aegis Research EU).

Their feedback enriched the dataset with lesser-known or context-specific initiatives and allowed triangulation of desk research findings.

Output of Step 1: a master Excel file compiling over 600+ candidate best practices, each documented with rich metadata (origin, actors, sector, and thematic focus) and qualitative descriptors (objectives, strategies, impact, transferability, alignment with EU policy priorities).

Best Practices identified cover various domains such as training and capacity building, joint incident response, policy harmonisation, technology sharing, and innovation support.

This long list of candidate practices (600+) served as the **baseline repository** for subsequent evaluation and filtering.

1.1.2.2. Step 2 – “Identification of shortlisted practices”

The objective of Step 2 is to **extract a refined shortlist of 20 high-potential practices**.

Each practice was reviewed and scored in the **same Excel repository**, ensuring consistency across assessments.

From the initial repository, a total of 20 candidate practices were shortlisted through the following three Steps:

1.1.2.2.1. Step 2.1. Shortlisting using predefined Inclusion and Exclusion criteria

Initial filtering was performed using predefined criteria, ensuring that only practices with demonstrable relevance, success, collaboration potential, and evidence base were retained. The scope was restricted to practices implemented within the EU27 or associated countries post-2015.

Inclusion criteria include:

- **Relevance to the topic:** the practice directly addresses cybersecurity challenges in civilian or defence sectors.
- **Effectiveness:** show success in mitigating threats, improving resilience, or enhancing coordination.
- **Scalability:** the practice shows a potential for adaptation across different regions, organisations, or sectors.
- **Collaboration:** encourages cross-sector cooperation between civilian and defence entities.
- **Evidence-based:** a practice is supported by case studies, data, or expert validation, for example.
- **Geographic and temporal settings:** practices are drawn from EU27 countries and associated countries, focusing on those implemented from 2015 onward.

1.1.2.2. Step 2.2. Shortlisting using Evaluation factors

Enriched filtering was performed to assess the candidate practices across seven dimensions: Feasibility, Impact, Efficiency, Scalability, Innovation, Risk Mitigation, and Ethical Considerations.

The scoring was performed to ensure a consistent evaluation and comparability across candidate practices.

Evaluation factors include:

- **Feasibility:** to assess the practicality of implementing each best practice based on available resources, regulatory constraints, and technical readiness.
- **Impact:** to measure the potential of the best practice to improve collaboration between the civilian and defence cybersecurity sectors.
- **Efficiency:** to evaluate how well the practice delivers high impact with minimal resources.
- **Scalability:** to evaluate the potential of each best practice to be expanded or adapted across various EU countries and sectors.

- **Innovation:** to measure whether a practice introduces new technologies, methodologies, approaches, or not.
- **Risk Mitigation:** to assess how well each best practice addresses known cybersecurity risks and mitigates potential challenges.
- **Ethical Considerations:** to assess the ethical implications of implementing the best practice, such as privacy concerns and data protection.

1.1.2.2.3. Step 2.3. Shortlisting using Keyword Mapping and Content Clustering

In parallel to Step 2.1 and Step 2.2, we used keyword mapping and content clustering to detect overlaps, trends, and unique features using qualitative coding techniques.

Particular attention was paid to **aligning practices with the 32 strategic actions identified in Deliverable D2.2**, creating a thematic bridge between the two studies.

Practices were mapped against strategic axes derived from Task 2.2 (e.g., policy harmonisation, shared training). This not only improved selection logic but ensured thematic continuity across the COcyber project.

Output of Step 2: a pre-validated shortlist of 11 promising best practices, categorised under emerging thematic families and ready for expert appraisal.

1.1.2.3. Step 3 – “Expert Validation and Rating”

The objective of Step 3 is to **confirm the operational value and transferability of the selected practices** through field-expert engagement.

This third step involved engaging a panel of **independent experts from the civil-defence sectors** to validate and refine the pre-validated shortlist of 11 promising best practices.

The expert insights guided the **ranking of the 11 candidate best practices**, which are documented and analysed in the present report. Each of them is accompanied by guidelines and commentary to support potential uptake, replication, or adaptation by relevant stakeholders across the EU cybersecurity ecosystem.

This validation process added an **external layer of credibility and operational relevance**, ensuring that the selected practices were not only theoretically sound but also field-tested and context-aware.

1.1.2.3.1. Step 3.1. Assessment of each practice against the agreed evaluation criteria

Each of the **20 practices was reviewed by a panel of domain experts** from both civil-defence backgrounds. They were asked to score practices using the same evaluation matrix and provide qualitative annotations to refine interpretation and flag missing elements.

The expert insights guided a ranking of the 11 best practices.

1.1.2.3.2. Step 3.2. Online consultation event: “Best Practice validation: Cybersecurity and Civil-Defence cooperation in the EU”

A panel of **independent experts** from both civilian and defence backgrounds was invited to validate the findings during a dedicated [COcyber interactive consultation event](#) held on 13th June 2025.

During this event, experts, Ambassadors, and Advisory Board members were asked to assess each practice based on predefined evaluation criteria and KPIs.

Using live interaction such as Microsoft Teams, Forms, and Excel, the panel:

- Reviewed and refined the shortlisting criteria.
- Provided scoring input on individual practices.
- Flagged potential omissions or misinterpretations.

Their input was essential to strengthen the legitimacy of the selected best practices and validate their relevance in real-world operational contexts.

Selection of the Final 11 Best Practices

Following the expert validation process (Step 3), the ULB team conducted a structured evaluation to identify the 11 most relevant and transferable best practices from the validated shortlist of 20.

Each practice was assessed and scored by two independent paid experts and some more volunteer experts through the validation workshop, using the agreed evaluation criteria: Feasibility, Impact, Efficiency, Scalability, Innovation, Risk Mitigation, and Ethical Considerations. Scores were compiled into a ranking table from 1 to 5.

The practices were then ordered by Total Points and Average Points across evaluators. The highest-ranking practices were selected as the final 11 Best Practices for civil-defence cooperation in cybersecurity.

This quantitative selection ensured:

- Transparency – scoring based on predefined and documented criteria.
- Comparability – consistent scoring across all practices.
- Robustness – expert-based validation reducing bias.

These 11 practices form the core set of transferable best practices will inform the guidelines and policy recommendations in Deliverables 4.2 and 4.5.

Output of Step 3: a finalised repository of 11 validated and rated best practices from across the EU on structured cybersecurity civil-defence cooperation.

The best practices were validated and rated by selected experts in the field according to a set of quality criteria and KPIs.

While this repository reflects a robust and systematic selection process, certain limitations should be acknowledged. Some practices may remain underrepresented due to gaps in publicly available data, varying levels of national reporting, or uneven geographical coverage. These constraints highlight the importance of continuous updates and future research to capture emerging practices and ensure that the repository remains comprehensive and representative over time.

Methodological note

To complement this methodological section, a detailed methodological note was produced at the beginning of Task 4.1. This document, titled *“Methodology for Identifying and Validating Best Practices”*, provides further clarification on the design rationale and analytical framework used throughout the research process.

It is annexed to this report for any reader wishing to explore the process in greater depth. (See [Appendix 1: Methodology for identifying and validating Best Practices.docx](#))

2 Best Practices

In the following sections, you will find the description of 11 best practices. These are accompanied by two tables, HOW and WHY, which explain, respectively, the practical steps for adopting each practice and the reasons each is considered a Structured Cybersecurity Civil-Defence Cooperation Best Practice. Both tables are grounded in the needs assessment documented in Deliverable D2.2, available at [COcyber D2.2 Needs Assessment Report](#) (See [Appendix 4](#)).

It is foreseen that the complete list of cybersecurity [practices](#), both civilian and defence-related, will be made available on the COcyber website ([Appendix 2](#)), together with a dedicated section highlighting the 11 practices identified as the best practices.

2.1 Best Practice 1: “Best Practices for Cyber Crisis Management”

Source: ENISA **Year:** 2024

Geographical Scope: Europe, with special emphasis on EU member states and their cybersecurity integration

Type: Integrated Crisis Management Frameworks

Thematic Domain: Cyber Crisis Management, Cybersecurity Best Practices, European Cybersecurity, Crisis Response, Defence and Civilian Spheres

Best Practice description

This study provides detailed best practices for managing cyber crises, focusing on frameworks that align with both defence and civilian sectors. The publication is part of ENISA’s ongoing efforts to enhance Europe’s resilience against cyber threats through structured crisis management strategies, collaborating across sectors and borders. The report presents a comprehensive analysis of current best practices, evaluating the integration of various stakeholders in handling cybersecurity incidents effectively.

Relevance to Civil-Defence Cooperation

WHY is this Best Practice considered a Structured Cybersecurity Civil-Defence Cooperation Best Practice?

This Best Practice is considered a Structured Cybersecurity Civil-Defence Cooperation Best Practice because it addresses the following identified needs:

- ✓ Fragmentation of cybersecurity efforts,
- ✓ Lack of (or limited) information-sharing,
- ✓ Lack of awareness capacity,
- ✓ Lack of coordinated cybersecurity policies,
- ✓ Lack of cross-pollination of ideas and best practices,
- ✓ Lack of cutting-edge innovation,

Recommendations for Adoption

HOW can this Best Practice be used to enhance Cybersecurity Civil-Defence Cooperation? – Identifying the key steps for adoption of the Best Practice

Joint Cyber Incident Response Teams, Real-Time Threat Intelligence Sharing Platforms, Joint Cybersecurity Training Programs, Cybersecurity Awareness Campaigns, Collaborative Threat Intelligence Networks, Develop Unified Policy Frameworks, Leverage International Best Practices, Develop Common Terminologies and Protocols, Trust-Building Activities, Vulnerability and Threat Analysis Policies, Unified Threat Intelligence (TI) and Early Warning Systems, Cross-Sector Vulnerability Disclosure Mechanisms.

Anticipated Benefits

- Strong stakeholder engagement.
- Clear communication protocols.
- Continued EU-wide cooperation.

Anticipated Challenges

- Variability in cybersecurity maturity across different EU states.
- Lack of universal resources and training for all sectors involved.

2.2 Best Practice 2: “ENISA Cybersecurity Skills Framework”

Source: [ENISA](#)

Year: 2022

Geographical Scope: The ECSF is designed for application across all EU Member States and associated countries. It supports the harmonisation of cybersecurity roles and competences across national education systems, employers, training providers, and certification bodies in the European Union.

Type: Real-Time Threat Intelligence Sharing Platforms

Thematic Domain: Cybersecurity Workforce Development, Civil-Military Cooperation, Threat Intelligence Sharing

Best Practice description

The European Cybersecurity Skills Framework (ECSF) is a structured reference model developed by the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA), published in 2022, to support a shared understanding of cybersecurity roles and competences across the EU Member States. It identifies 12 key cybersecurity professional profiles, detailing their associated tasks, knowledge, skills, and responsibilities.

The framework serves as a common language between employers, educators, training providers, and policymakers, enabling better alignment between workforce needs and skills development. By promoting standardised role definitions, the ECSF helps reduce fragmentation, supports workforce planning, and facilitates the recognition of cybersecurity qualifications across borders.

The ECSF contributes to broader EU strategies such as the Digital Education Action Plan, the European Skills Agenda, and the Cybersecurity Strategy for the Digital Decade, playing a central role in strengthening Europe's cyber workforce and addressing the skills gap in both the civilian and public sectors.

Relevance to Civil-Defence Cooperation

WHY is this Best Practice considered a Structured Cybersecurity Civil-Defence Cooperation Best Practice?

This Best Practice is considered a Structured Cybersecurity Civil-Defence Cooperation Best Practice because it addresses the following identified needs:

- ✓ Fragmentation of cybersecurity efforts,
- ✓ Lack of (or limited) information-sharing,

- ✓ Lack of coordinated cybersecurity policies,
- ✓ Lack of cross-pollination of ideas and best practices,
- ✓ Cultural differences between the two sectors.

Recommendations for Adoption

HOW can this Best Practice be used to enhance Cybersecurity Civil-Defence Cooperation? – Identifying the key steps for adoption of the Best Practice

Joint Cyber Incident Response Teams, Real-Time Threat Intelligence Sharing Platforms, Integrated Crisis Management Frameworks, Shared Resource Allocation, Cybersecurity Governance Framework, Public-Private Cybersecurity Partnerships, National Cybersecurity Simulations, Cross-Sector Crisis Management, Cross-Sector Cybersecurity Workshops, Collaborative Threat Intelligence Networks, Develop Unified Policy Frameworks, Leverage International Best Practices, Trust-Building Activities, Vulnerability and Threat Analysis Policies, Shared Funding and Resources, Unified Threat Intelligence (TI) and Early Warning Systems, Cross-Sector Vulnerability Disclosure Mechanisms.

Anticipated Benefits

- Clear structure and user-friendly role profiles.
- Endorsement by ENISA and alignment with EU digital and cybersecurity strategies.
- Flexibility to apply across sectors, education systems, and job markets.
- Supports harmonisation in cybersecurity education, training, and certification.

Anticipated Challenges

- Limited direct defence sector integration to date.
- Adoption varies across Member States and sectors.
- Requires ongoing updates to reflect emerging roles (e.g., AI safety, quantum security).
- Resource constraints for smaller organisations and training providers to fully implement.

2.3 Best Practice 3: “Cyber Attacks in Times of Conflict”

Source: Cybil Portal | CyberPeace Institute

Year: 2022

Geographical Scope: The report distinguishes between three main geographic zones in terms of incident distribution and targets. In Ukraine, 574 incidents were recorded, primarily affecting public administration, financial services, ICT, media, and transportation sectors. In the Russian Federation, 306 incidents were documented, including attacks on public administration, transportation, ICT systems, and widespread defacement/DDoS campaigns, particularly in annexed territories. In addition, 1,896 incidents were reported in other countries outside the direct conflict zone, with Poland (315), Lithuania (157), Germany (136), the United States (101), and Estonia (93) among the most affected. These countries, largely EU Member States or partners providing military, political, or humanitarian support to Ukraine were predominantly targeted with DDoS attacks against public administration, transport, and financial services. This classification reflects the geographical spread of incidents and the associated targets, rather than attributing practices or responses to a single country.

Type: Unified Threat Intelligence (TI) and Early Warning Systems

Thematic Domain: defence, civilians

Best Practice description

This tool monitors the harm to civilians from cyberattacks. It also provides insight into: Cyber Threats: Analysing attacks & attribution to reach legal accountability. Impact & Harm: Tracing harm to civilians to protect civilians. Law & Policy: Documenting legal instruments to drive regulatory change.

Relevance to Civil-Defence Cooperation

WHY is this Best Practice considered a Structured Cybersecurity Civil-Defence Cooperation Best Practice?

This Best Practice is considered a Structured Cybersecurity Civil-Defence Cooperation Best Practice because it addresses the following identified needs:

- ✓ Fragmentation of cybersecurity efforts,
- ✓ Lack of (or limited) information-sharing,
- ✓ Lack of awareness capacity,
- ✓ Lack of coordinated cybersecurity policies,

- ✓ Lack of cross-pollination of ideas and best practices,
- ✓ Cultural differences between the two sectors.

Recommendations for Adoption

HOW can this Best Practice be used to enhance Cybersecurity Civil-Defence Cooperation? – Identifying the key steps for adoption of the Best Practice

Unified Threat Intelligence (TI) and Early Warning Systems, Vulnerability and Threat Analysis Policies, Cybersecurity Awareness Campaigns, Develop Unified Policy Frameworks, Public-Private Cybersecurity Partnerships, Promote Cross-Sector Policy Dialogue, Trust-Building Activities, Cross-Sector Vulnerability Disclosure Mechanisms, Leverage International Best Practices, Cultural Exchange Initiatives

Anticipated Benefits

- Human-centric approach focused on real-world consequences.
- Strong use of data transparency and open-source intelligence.
- A highly engaged global volunteer network bridges the gap between private-sector expertise and civil-society needs.
- Collaboration with EU-funded projects, such as those under Horizon 2020, strengthens reach and credibility.

Anticipated Challenges

- Limited operational scope due to resource constraints.
- Risks related to political sensitivities when attributing attacks.
- Dependence on open-source data, which may miss classified or covert operations.
- Requires complex cross-sector coordination.

2.4 Best Practice 4: “Cyber Rapid Response Teams”

Source: Cyber Rapid Response Teams under EU's PESCO initiative | CSS (Centre for Security Studies)

Year: 2023

Geographical Scope: Primarily Europe, with a specific focus on integrating both defence and civilian cybersecurity infrastructures.

Type: Joint Cyber Incident Response Teams

Thematic Domain: Cybersecurity, Rapid Response Teams, Crisis Management, Cyber Defence

Best Practice description

The practice focuses on the concept, effectiveness, and challenges of establishing and implementing Cyber Rapid Response Teams (CRRTs). These teams are structured to react quickly to large-scale cyber incidents and collaborate with both defence and civilian sectors, particularly in Europe. It highlights the role of collaboration, scalability, and preparedness in mitigating cyber threats and outlines how these teams can function effectively in rapidly evolving cyber crises.

Relevance to Civil-Defence Cooperation

WHY is this Best Practice considered a Structured Cybersecurity Civil-Defence Cooperation Best Practice?

This Best Practice is considered a Structured Cybersecurity Civil-Defence Cooperation Best Practice because it addresses the following identified needs:

- ✓ Fragmentation of cybersecurity efforts,
- ✓ Lack of (or limited) information-sharing,
- ✓ Lack of awareness capacity,
- ✓ Lack of coordinated cybersecurity policies,
- ✓ Lack of cross-pollination of ideas and best practices,
- ✓ Lack of cutting-edge innovation.

Recommendations for Adoption

HOW can this Best Practice be used to enhance Cybersecurity Civil-Defence Cooperation? – Identifying the key steps for adoption of the Best Practice

Joint Cyber Incident Response Teams, Real-Time Threat Intelligence Sharing Platforms, Joint Cybersecurity Training Programs, Integrated Crisis Management Frameworks, Shared Resource Allocation, Harmonised Cybersecurity Framework, Cybersecurity Governance Framework, Public-Private Cybersecurity Partnerships, Cross-Sector Crisis Management, Cybersecurity Awareness Campaigns, Collaborative Threat Intelligence Networks, Develop Unified Policy

Frameworks, Promote Cross-Sector Policy Dialogue, Leverage International Best Practices, Develop Common Terminologies and Protocols, Trust-Building Activities, Fast Reorganisation Programs, Vulnerability and Threat Analysis Policies, Shared Funding and Resources, Long-Term Collaboration Agreements, Unified Threat Intelligence (TI) and Early Warning Systems, Cross-Sector Vulnerability Disclosure Mechanisms, Simplify Technology Transfer Processes, Launch Joint Cybersecurity R&D Initiatives, Exchange Programs, Streamline Compliance Processes, Create Cybersecurity Innovation Hubs.

Anticipated Benefits

-Effective leadership, timely responses, strong inter-sector collaboration, and appropriate funding.

Anticipated Challenges

-Coordination between sectors, maintaining team readiness, and ensuring long-term sustainability.

2.5 Best Practice 5: “SIM3: Security Incident Management Maturity Model”

Source: Cybil Portal | Don Stikvoort, Open CSIRT Foundation

Year identified: 2015

Geographical Scope: Primarily adopted in Europe (EU27) through the TF-CSIRT / Trusted Introducer community, but also relevant to APCERT, LACNIC, Africa CERT, and other regional and global CSIRT networks. It is used internationally by national, sectoral, and corporate CERTs/CSIRTs, including in associated countries.

Type: Cybersecurity Governance Framework

Thematic Domain: Integrated Crisis Management Frameworks

Best Practice description

The practice focuses on evaluating and improving the maturity of Security Incident Management (SIM) capabilities through the SIM3 model. SIM is treated as a holistic process comprising four core pillars: prevention, detection, resolution, and quality control with feedback. The main scope covers IT and information security incidents—those affecting computers, network devices, and the data transmitted

or stored within them. The model, however, is adaptable and can be applied to wider or narrower scopes as appropriate. For clarity and ease of reference, the term "CSIRT" is used throughout to describe any capability—whether a team, service, or function—that is subject to SIM3 assessment, even though "ISIMC" (Information Security Incident Management Capability) is more accurate. It is also noted that "CERT", a term commonly used interchangeably with CSIRT, is a trademark owned by Carnegie Mellon University in the United States and should only be used with proper authorisation. This practice provides a structured means for organisations to benchmark and enhance their incident management maturity.

Relevance to Civil-Defence Cooperation

WHY is this Best Practice considered a Structured Cybersecurity Civil-Defence Cooperation Best Practice?

This Best Practice is considered a Structured Cybersecurity Civil-Defence Cooperation Best Practice because it addresses the following identified needs:

- ✓ Fragmentation of cybersecurity efforts,
- ✓ Lack of (or limited) information-sharing,
- ✓ Lack of awareness capacity,
- ✓ Lack of coordinated cybersecurity policies,
- ✓ Lack of cross-pollination of ideas and best practices.

Recommendations for Adoption

HOW can this Best Practice be used to enhance Cybersecurity Civil-Defence Cooperation? – Identifying the key steps for adoption of the Best Practice

The SIM3 model from the Open CSIRT Foundation can strengthen Cybersecurity–Civil Defence cooperation by offering a structured way to assess and improve incident response maturity. By benchmarking CSIRTs across governance, people, processes, and tools, it builds trust, interoperability, and a common baseline, enabling more effective joint preparedness, crisis coordination, and resilient responses to cyber–physical threats.

Anticipated Benefits

- Wide community adoption: Recognised by European and global CSIRT networks (e.g., TF-CSIRT, FIRST, APCERT).
- Balanced design: Covers governance, process, and technical dimensions equally, ensuring holistic maturity evaluation.
- Certifiable and trust-building: Forms the core of TI's certification process, adding institutional trust across EU CSIRTs.
- Simplicity and clarity: Clearly defined parameters and maturity levels make it accessible to teams at different development stages.

Anticipated Challenges

- Requires time and engagement: Full assessment and implementation can be resource-intensive, especially for smaller teams.
- Not fully automated: It relies on qualitative judgment and interviews, limiting speed and scale of mass assessments.
- Voluntary model: SIM3 is not legally mandated, so uptake may depend on network incentives or peer pressure.
- Sustainability of updates: Regular updating is required to align with evolving threats and CSIRT functions (though this is managed well by Open CSIRT Foundation).

2.6 Best Practice 6: "IBM X-Force Exchange"

Source: Cybil Portal | IBM

Year of Launch: 2015

Geographical Scope: Global reach, with data and users spanning over 130 countries, including EU27 nations and associated countries.

Type: Real-Time Threat Intelligence Sharing Platforms

Thematic Domain: Dual-Use Technology Agreements

Best Practice description

IBM X-Force Exchange is a cloud-based, threat intelligence sharing platform that you can use to rapidly research the latest global security threats, aggregate actionable intelligence, consult with experts, and collaborate with peers. IBM X-Force Exchange, supported by human- and machine-generated intelligence, leverages the scale of IBM X-Force to help users stay ahead of emerging threats.

Relevance to Civil-Defence Cooperation

WHY is this Best Practice considered a Structured Cybersecurity Civil-Defence Cooperation Best Practice?

This Best Practice is considered a Structured Cybersecurity Civil-Defence Cooperation Best Practice because it addresses the following identified needs:

- ✓ Fragmentation of cybersecurity efforts,
- ✓ Lack of information-sharing,
- ✓ Lack of awareness capacity,
- ✓ Lack of coordinated cybersecurity policies
- ✓ Lack of cross-pollination of ideas and best practices,
- ✓ Lack of cutting-edge innovation

Recommendations for Adoption

HOW can this Best Practice be used to enhance Cybersecurity Civil-Defence Cooperation? – Identifying the key steps for adoption of the Best Practice

IBM X-Force Exchange enhances Cybersecurity Civil-Defence Cooperation by enabling real-time, trusted threat intelligence sharing across sectors and borders. Its global reach, interoperability, and collaborative model strengthen early warning, speed up responses, and improve resilience in critical sectors, providing a practical bridge between civil and defence stakeholders.

Anticipated Benefits

- High trust and brand legitimacy due to IBM's reputation and cybersecurity expertise.
- Strong technical interoperability (supports key standards like STIX, TAXII).
- User engagement model encourages curated contributions from industry experts.
- Enables shared situational awareness across industries, geographies, and critical sectors.

Anticipated Challenges

- Participation asymmetry: some users consume data without contributing ("free riders").
- Overreliance on English-language content, which may limit reach and contextual sensitivity.

- Requires active human curation to maintain quality, which can slow real-time benefits.
- Some organisations may hesitate to share sensitive indicators due to legal or reputational concerns.

2.7 Best Practice 7: “GFCE Global Good Practices National Computer Security Incident Response Teams (CSIRTs)”

Source: Cybil Portal | Global Forum on Cyber Expertise (GFCE)

Year of Launch: 2017

Geographical Scope: Global, but directly applicable to EU27 countries, associated states, and partner countries. Practices referenced from EU Member States (e.g., Estonia, the Netherlands), NATO-aligned states, and GFCE members, many of which are part of European cyber cooperation frameworks.

Type: Joint Cyber Incident Response Teams

Thematic Domain: Real-Time Threat Intelligence Sharing Platforms

Best Practice description

Even the best cybersecurity posture and practices cannot guarantee that key organisations and information infrastructures within a nation will not be vulnerable to malware, software failures, human errors, and other mishaps. The cyber threat landscape changes rapidly. Cyber incidents occur on a daily basis and may be of cross-border, multinational, and often even global nature. Nowadays, threat actors target specific individuals, organisations, industries, and nations, or may indiscriminately target any system. Therefore, it is crucial for nations to take their responsibility and build an effective national CSIRT capacity.

Relevance to Civil-Defence Cooperation

WHY is this Best Practice considered a Structured Cybersecurity Civil-Defence Cooperation Best Practice?

This Best Practice is considered a Structured Cybersecurity Civil-Defence Cooperation Best Practice because it addresses the following identified needs:

- ✓ Fragmentation of cybersecurity efforts,

- ✓ Lack of (or limited) information-sharing,
- ✓ Lack of awareness capacity
- ✓ Lack of coordinated cybersecurity policies
- ✓ Lack of cross-pollination of ideas and best practices
- ✓ Cultural differences between the two sectors.

Recommendations for Adoption

HOW can this Best Practice be used to enhance Cybersecurity Civil-Defence Cooperation? – Identifying the key steps for adoption of the Best Practice

The GFCE Global Good Practices on National CSIRTs provide a structured framework that can greatly enhance cybersecurity civil-defence cooperation by institutionalising trust, improving cross-border interoperability, and formalising rapid incident response mechanisms. By creating joint cyber incident response teams based on these guidelines, civil authorities, defence actors, and critical infrastructure operators can coordinate in real time, share actionable threat intelligence, and align escalation protocols. This reduces fragmentation, ensures faster crisis containment, and strengthens collective resilience against both domestic and multinational cyber threats.

Anticipated Benefits

- Governmental commitment and political will to institutionalise CSIRT operations.
- Legal and policy clarity around mandates, information handling, and sectoral roles.
- Operational trust through participation in multilateral networks (FIRST, EU CSIRT Network).
- Sustainable funding and continuous skills development.
- Clear escalation and communication protocols for national and cross-sector coordination.

Anticipated Challenges

- Resource gaps in emerging economies or newly established teams.
- Overlap and competition between national and sectoral CERTs if governance is weak.
- Information sensitivity and trust issues limiting proactive information sharing.

- Legal and procedural divergence in multijurisdictional incident response.
- Staff retention due to market pressure on skilled cyber professionals.

2.8 Best Practice 8: “Exporting Dual-Use Items”

Source: European Commission – Directorate-General for Trade

Year identified: 2021

Geographical Scope: European Union

Type: Dual-Use Technology Agreements

Thematic Domain: Dual-use items, export control, cybersecurity, EU Regulation 2021/821, encryption, cyber-surveillance

Best Practice description

This practice outlines the EU's regulatory framework for controlling the export of dual-use items—goods, software, and technology applicable to both civilian and military uses. It details the types of export authorisations, compliance requirements, and the scope of items covered, including those related to cybersecurity and encryption.

Relevance to Civil-Defence Cooperation

WHY is this Best Practice considered a Structured Cybersecurity Civil-Defence Cooperation Best Practice?

This Best Practice is considered a Structured Cybersecurity Civil-Defence Cooperation Best Practice because it addresses the following identified needs:

- ✓ Fragmentation of cybersecurity efforts,
- ✓ Lack of (or limited) information-sharing,
- ✓ Lack of awareness capacity,
- ✓ Lack of coordinated cybersecurity policies,
- ✓ Lack of cross-pollination of ideas and best practices,
- ✓ Lack of cutting-edge innovation.

Recommendations for Adoption

HOW can this Best Practice be used to enhance Cybersecurity Civil-Defence Cooperation? – Identifying the key steps for adoption of the Best Practice

Joint Cyber Incident Response Teams, Real-Time Threat Intelligence Sharing Platforms, Integrated Crisis Management Frameworks, Shared Resource Allocation, Harmonised Cybersecurity Framework, Cybersecurity Governance Framework, Public-Private Cybersecurity Partnerships, National Cybersecurity Simulations, Cross-Sector Crisis Management, Cross-Sector Cybersecurity Workshops, Cybersecurity Awareness Campaigns, Collaborative Threat Intelligence Networks, Develop Unified Policy Frameworks, Leverage International Best Practices, Develop Common Terminologies and Protocols, Trust-Building Activities, Vulnerability and Threat Analysis Policies, Shared Funding and Resources, Unified Threat Intelligence (TI) and Early Warning Systems, Cross-Sector Vulnerability Disclosure Mechanisms.

Anticipated Benefits

-Alignment with international regimes, clear regulatory framework, and cooperation among member states.

Anticipated Challenges

-Keeping pace with rapid technological advancements and ensuring compliance among diverse stakeholders.

2.9 Best Practice 9: “Cybersecurity / Information Analysis R&D”

Source: U.S. Department of Homeland Security (DHS), Science and Technology Directorate | Department of Homeland Security (DHS)

Year identified: 2025

Geographical Scope: Primarily United States; potential applicability to international partners

Type: Launch Joint Cybersecurity R&D Initiatives

Thematic Domain: Cybersecurity, Information Analysis, R&D, Critical Infrastructure, AI, Machine Learning, Data Privacy, Software Assurance

Best Practice description

DHS fosters joint R&D with industry and academia to develop advanced cybersecurity tools, focusing on threat detection, secure software, and AI-enabled defences for both civilian and defence use.

Relevance to Civil-Defence Cooperation

WHY is this Best Practice considered a Structured Cybersecurity Civil-Defence Cooperation Best Practice?

This Best Practice is considered a Structured Cybersecurity Civil-Defence Cooperation Best Practice because it addresses the following identified needs:

- ✓ Fragmentation of cybersecurity efforts,
- ✓ Lack of (or limited) information-sharing
- ✓ Lack of dual-use technologies
- ✓ Lack of cross-pollination of ideas and best practices
- ✓ Lack of cutting-edge innovation

Recommendations for Adoption

HOW can this Best Practice be used to enhance Cybersecurity Civil-Defence Cooperation? – Identifying the key steps for adoption of the Best Practice

This practice can enhance Cybersecurity Civil-Defence cooperation by fostering joint R&D projects between government, industry, and academia to develop advanced tools for threat detection, secure software, and AI-enabled defences. By adapting the DHS model to European or international contexts, civilian and defence actors can jointly strengthen critical infrastructure protection, share innovations, and build interoperable solutions that address fast-evolving cyber threats.

Anticipated Benefits

-Effective collaboration and innovation drive success, but measurable outcomes vary.

Anticipated Challenges

-Realistic but not deeply analysed; fast-evolving threats pose persistent issues.

2.10 Best Practice 10: “CyberPeace Builders”

Source: Cybil Portal | CyberPeace Institute

Year: 2021

Geographical Scope: CPB operates globally, supporting NGOs in over 50 countries, including those within the EU27.

Type: Public-Private Cybersecurity Partnerships

Thematic Domain: Joint Cybersecurity Training Programs

Best Practice description

The CyberPeace Builders is a global network of corporate volunteers coordinated by the CyberPeace Institute, providing free pre- and post-incident assistance to Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs) protecting vulnerable populations. Developed in 2020 after consultations and pilot phases, the program ensures that NGOs in critical civilian sectors—such as healthcare, energy, food and agriculture, and water and sanitation—can access industry-grade expertise. Support includes security assessments, awareness-raising, training, and incident-response capability building, as well as post-incident hardening measures to avoid reinfection. Regional advisors act as liaisons to ensure a localised and contextualised approach. This initiative directly contributes to the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 16 by strengthening NGO resilience, protecting sensitive data, building donor trust, and ensuring continuity of vital services.

Relevance to Civil-Defence Cooperation

WHY is this Best Practice considered a Structured Cybersecurity Civil-Defence Cooperation Best Practice?

This Best Practice is considered a Structured Cybersecurity Civil-Defence Cooperation Best Practice because it addresses the following identified needs:

- ✓ Fragmentation of cybersecurity efforts,
- ✓ Lack of (or limited) information-sharing,
- ✓ Lack of awareness capacity,
- ✓ Lack of coordinated cybersecurity policies,
- ✓ Lack of cross-pollination of ideas and best practices.

Recommendations for Adoption

HOW can this Best Practice be used to enhance Cybersecurity Civil-Defence Cooperation? – Identifying the key steps for adoption of the Best Practice

Harmonised Cybersecurity Framework, Cybersecurity Governance Framework, Public-Private Cybersecurity Partnerships, Cross-Sector Cybersecurity Workshops, Cybersecurity Awareness Campaigns, Collaborative Threat Intelligence Networks, Develop Unified Policy Frameworks, Leverage International Best Practices, Develop Common Terminologies and Protocols, Trust-Building Activities, Vulnerability and Threat Analysis Policies, Shared Funding and Resources, Unified Threat Intelligence (TI) and Early Warning Systems, Cross-Sector Vulnerability Disclosure Mechanisms.

Anticipated Benefits

- Strong partnerships with industry leaders (e.g., Microsoft, Mastercard, SAP, Deloitte).
- A clear value proposition for both NGOs (free support) and corporate volunteers (CSR, skill development).
- Structured, ethical volunteer framework and onboarding.
- Global coverage with scalable digital coordination.

Anticipated Challenges

- Limited capacity of NGOs to adopt or maintain even free cyber support if internal skills remain low.
- Time availability of volunteers can fluctuate.
- Coordination complexity when managing multi-lingual, cross-time zone engagements.
- Requires trust-building and clarity around data sensitivity and liability.

2.11 Best Practice 11: “International Cybersecurity Information Sharing Agreements”

Source: Cybersecurity and Information Sharing | University of Maryland and various cybersecurity professionals

Year: 2017

Geographical Scope: Global, with a particular focus on Europe and international collaborations

Type: Joint Cyber Incident Response Teams

Thematic Domain: Cybersecurity, Information Sharing, International Agreements, Threat Intelligence, Collaboration, Defence, Civilian Spheres

Best Practice description

The practice explores the development and challenges of international agreements for cybersecurity information sharing between countries, focusing on how to establish effective frameworks to protect against cyber threats. It covers the role of Joint Cyber Incident Response Teams (J-CIRTs) and cross-border collaboration for handling cyberattacks and other threats in both defence and civilian sectors.

Relevance to Civil-Defence Cooperation

WHY is this Best Practice considered a Structured Cybersecurity Civil-Defence Cooperation Best Practice?

This Best Practice is considered a Structured Cybersecurity Civil-Defence Cooperation Best Practice because it addresses the following identified needs:

- ✓ Fragmentation of cybersecurity efforts,
- ✓ Lack of (or limited) information-sharing,
- ✓ Lack of awareness capacity,
- ✓ Lack of coordinated cybersecurity policies,
- ✓ Lack of cross-pollination of ideas and best practices,
- ✓ Lack of cutting-edge innovation.

Recommendations for Adoption

HOW can this Best Practice be used to enhance Cybersecurity Civil-Defence Cooperation? – Identifying the key steps for adoption of the Best Practice

Joint Cyber Incident Response Teams, Real-Time Threat Intelligence Sharing Platforms, Joint Cybersecurity Training Programs, Integrated Crisis Management Frameworks, Cybersecurity Governance Framework, Public-Private Cybersecurity Partnerships, Cross-Sector Crisis Management, Cybersecurity Awareness Campaigns, Collaborative Threat Intelligence Networks, Develop Unified Policy Frameworks, Leverage International Best Practices, Develop Common Terminologies and Protocols, Trust-Building Activities, Vulnerability

and Threat Analysis Policies, Unified Threat Intelligence (TI) and Early Warning Systems, Cross-Sector Vulnerability Disclosure Mechanisms.

Anticipated Benefits

- Effective governance frameworks and standardised procedures for information sharing
- Commitment from both civilian and defence sectors across borders
- Development of trust-building activities to ensure transparency and cooperation

Anticipated Challenges

- Political and jurisdictional barriers to information sharing
- Differences in national cybersecurity capabilities and maturity levels
- Data privacy and ethical concerns when sharing sensitive information across borders

3 Recommendations on Guidelines for Enhancing Civil-Defence Cybersecurity Cooperation

Based on the comprehensive analysis of 11 best practices, the following recommendations outline strategic, operational, and policy actions designed to strengthen collaboration between the civilian and defence cybersecurity sectors.

These recommendations aim to maximise synergies, address identified gaps and foster sustainable cooperation at the EU and national levels.

By systematically implementing these recommendations, the EU and its Member States can build a resilient, unified cybersecurity posture that effectively bridges civilian and defence spheres. This approach will enhance the collective ability to anticipate, prevent, and respond to the complex cyber threats of today and tomorrow.

3.1 Guideline 1: Establish and Promote Common Threat Intelligence Frameworks

Through the identification of the 20 best practices cited in the previous section, we identified the following guidelines:

Action	Description of the Action and link to best practice
Adopt Shared Taxonomies and Platforms	Implement widely accepted frameworks such as MITRE ATT&CK and ENISA’s Threat Landscape as foundational tools for both civil-defence stakeholders. These tools should be integrated into joint intelligence platforms to provide a unified view of evolving threats and adversary behaviours.
Facilitate Real-Time Information Sharing	Develop secure, scalable channels and protocols that enable the timely exchange of threat intelligence, alerts, and incident data across sectors and borders. Emphasise interoperability and data standardisation to reduce barriers.
Encourage Collaborative Reporting	Jointly produce threat assessments and situational reports modelled on the UK NSA or EU IOCTA, ensuring these are actionable and accessible to both civil-defence actors.

3.2 Guideline 2: Harmonise Governance Frameworks and Risk Management Practices

Through the identification of the 20 best practices cited in the previous section, we identified the following guidelines:

Action	Description of the Action and link to best practice
Align Risk and Governance Models	Promote the adoption of flexible but structured governance frameworks like NIST CSF 2.0 and COBIT 2019 across sectors. Facilitate alignment workshops to ensure a common understanding of objectives, roles, and accountability.
Implement Sector-Specific Maturity Models	Utilise maturity assessment tools such as PROGRESS CCMM and SIM3 to benchmark and develop cybersecurity capabilities, with an emphasis on harmonising maturity levels between civil-defence organisations.
Create Joint Governance Bodies	Establish or strengthen cross-sector steering committees or boards tasked with overseeing cooperative cybersecurity strategies, policy alignment, and resource allocation. Particular emphasis should be placed on the active involvement of industry associations, telecom providers, and critical infrastructure operators, whose

	participation helps ensure that governance frameworks remain practical, market-relevant, and aligned with private-sector realities.
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3.3 Guideline 3: Expand Joint Training, Exercises, and Capacity Building

Through the identification of the 20 best practices cited in the previous section, we identified the following guidelines:

Action	Description of the Action and link to best practice
Design and Conduct Regular Joint Exercises	Build upon models like ENISA’s Election Cyber Exercise and Cyber Crisis Management best practices by creating scenario-based exercises that simulate complex cyber incidents affecting both civilian and defence infrastructures.
Develop Cross-Sector Training Programs	Leverage frameworks such as the ENISA Cybersecurity Skills Framework to design curricula that enhance workforce interoperability and mobility between sectors. Encourage certifications and continuous professional development aligned with shared competencies.
Promote Knowledge Sharing Platforms	Facilitate communities of practice, workshops, and conferences that foster exchange of lessons learned, innovative solutions, and operational experiences. Particular attention should also be given to regional and cross-border initiatives—such as Baltic or Nordic exercises—that strengthen cooperation and build resilience in regions facing shared threat landscapes.

3.4 Guideline 4: Foster Legal and Policy Harmonisation

Through the identification of the 20 best practices cited in the previous section, we identified the following guidelines:

Action	Description of the Action and link to best practice
Standardise Incident Notification and Data Sharing Protocols	Encourage Member States to adopt common guidelines inspired by Spain’s National Incident Management Guide and EU directives like NIS2 to facilitate efficient cross-sector and cross-border communication.
Address Data Protection and Privacy Challenges	Develop harmonised frameworks that balance security needs with privacy and ethical considerations, ensuring compliance with GDPR and other relevant regulations.
Support Policy Coordination at the EU Level	Utilise EU institutions to mediate and align national policies affecting cybersecurity cooperation, including public procurement, critical infrastructure protection, and research funding.

3.5 Guideline 5: Promote Operational Integration and Interoperability

Through the identification of the 20 best practices cited in the previous section, we identified the following guidelines:

Action	Description of the Action and link to best practice
Develop Integrated Incident Response Frameworks	Draw from SEI’s CSIRT guidance and SIM3 maturity model to build interoperable response teams capable of coordinated action during cyber incidents affecting both civil-defence assets.
Implement Shared Tools and Platforms	Invest in joint cyber situational awareness platforms and response tools that facilitate synchronised monitoring, detection, and mitigation efforts.
Encourage Pilot Projects for Collaborative Operations	Launch EU-funded pilot initiatives that demonstrate the feasibility and benefits of operational civil-defence cooperation in cybersecurity, incorporating lessons learned into broader deployment plans.

3.6 Guideline 6: Address Workforce and Resource Challenges

Through the identification of the 20 best practices cited in the previous section, we identified the following guidelines:

Action	Description of the Action and link to best practice
Enhance Talent Mobility and Skills Alignment	Use the ENISA Skills Framework to develop talent pipelines that support cross-sector recruitment, rotation, and retention strategies.
Allocate Dedicated Funding for Capacity Building	Advocate for targeted EU and national funding streams that support joint training, research, and operational cooperation initiatives.
Encourage Public-Private Partnerships	Engage industry stakeholders in capacity building and knowledge sharing, recognising their critical role in the cybersecurity ecosystem.

3.7 Guideline 7: Continuous Monitoring, Evaluation, and Improvement

Through the identification of the 20 best practices cited in the previous section, we identified the following guidelines:

Action	Description of the Action and link to best practice
Establish Feedback Mechanisms	Implement processes for regular evaluation of cooperation initiatives, using maturity models and performance metrics to guide improvements.
Leverage Lessons Learned	Capture insights from joint exercises, incidents, and research to continuously refine strategies and operational practices.
Promote Research and Innovation	Support studies addressing emerging technologies and threats, ensuring cooperation frameworks remain forward-looking and adaptive.

4 Conclusions

This report constitutes a pivotal contribution within the broader COcyber project, which seeks to enhance structured cooperation between civilian and defence cybersecurity stakeholders across the European Union.

By identifying and analysing twenty exemplary best practices from diverse national and international experiences, it provides an essential knowledge base to inform the project's subsequent phases and overall objectives. The identification and analysis of 11 best practices across the EU reveal a rich and diverse ecosystem of structured initiatives designed to enhance cybersecurity cooperation between civilian and defence sectors. These best practices collectively demonstrate how systematic collaboration, shared frameworks, and joint operational efforts significantly improve national and European cyber resilience.

The findings underscore the necessity of strong leadership, shared frameworks and language, mutual trust, and inclusive governance as foundational elements to overcome traditional sectoral divisions. The adaptability of cooperation mechanisms, ongoing capacity building, and institutionalised learning processes emerge as critical for achieving sustainable and resilient civil-defence cybersecurity collaboration.

Importantly, this work demonstrates that effective cooperation extends beyond isolated initiatives, requiring a systemic and holistic approach that promotes cross-sector coordination, resource sharing, and policy alignment. The recommendations formulated here directly support COcyber's mission to foster a coherent European cybersecurity ecosystem capable of facing increasingly complex and hybrid cyber threats.

As the COcyber project progresses toward detailed national case studies and the development of actionable operational guidelines, this report offers a solid framework to guide stakeholders in harmonising strategies and practices. Ultimately, COcyber's integrated approach advances the vision of a unified, agile, and well-prepared European cyberspace where civilian and defence actors jointly safeguard critical digital infrastructures.

By consolidating these efforts, the COcyber project positions the EU to strengthen its cyber resilience and strategic autonomy in a rapidly evolving threat landscape.

5 Appendix 1–Methodology for identifying and validating Best Practices

5.1 Intro

This document introduces the **Methodology for identifying and validating Best Practices** in structured cybersecurity civil-defence cooperation across the EU. The approach involves identifying at least 10 best practices, which will be systematically assessed and validated by selected experts in the field. The validation process will follow a structured framework based on a set of predefined **quality criteria and key performance indicators (KPIs)** to ensure relevance, effectiveness, and transferability. The outcomes of this methodology will be presented in **Deliverable D.4.1**, which will compile the selected best practices and provide cooperation guidelines tailored for stakeholders in both the civilian and defence cybersecurity sectors. This methodology ensures a rigorous and objective selection process, fostering actionable insights and enhancing cybersecurity collaboration across Europe.

Disclaimer:

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Cybersecurity Competence Centre. Neither the European Union nor the European Cybersecurity Competence Centre can be held responsible for them.

5.2 Methodology steps

5.2.1 Literature review and desk research

Goals and methods: Conduct an extensive review of existing practices and initiatives implemented across various EU countries. The goal is to compile a comprehensive list of relevant practices.

Complementary data collection methods: While literature review and desk research remain the core methodology, additional approaches will be integrated to enhance the comprehensiveness of data collection. These include:

- Stakeholder submissions for best practices: a structured call for contributions will be launched to engage key cybersecurity and defence stakeholders across Europe. This initiative aims to collect and document effective best practices that may not yet be formally published. Organisations will have the opportunity to submit their best practices through a designated submission form through Microsoft Forms (based on [Template of Best Practices](#)), ensuring a systematic and transparent data collection process.
- Collaboration with active initiatives: engagement with ongoing EU-funded cybersecurity projects and initiatives, such as ECYBRIDGE, to identify recent best practices not documented in academic literature.
- Desk research expansion: beyond literature review, an emphasis will be placed on grey literature, industry reports, cybersecurity frameworks, and government policy documents. This approach ensures that practical, on-the-ground implementations are captured.

The search strategy for identifying the practices:

- Data sources to be used: NATO Cooperative Cyber Defence Centre of Excellence library², Cybil Knowledge Portal of the Global Forum on Cyber Expertise (GFCE)³, Cybersecurity Observatory of European Commission⁴, World Economic Forum Centre for Cybersecurity⁵, European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA)⁶, DIGITALEUROPE⁷ and others.
- Keywords (Alignment with D2.2: A.1–A.32 solutions): Joint Cyber Incident Response Teams, Dual-Use Technology Agreements, Real-Time Threat Intelligence Sharing

² NATO Cooperative Cyber Defence Centre of Excellence. (n.d.). CCDCOE. Retrieved March 12, 2025, from <https://ccdcoe.org/library/publications/>

³ Cybil Knowledge Portal of the Global Forum on Cyber Expertise (GFCE). Retrieved March 12, 2025, from <https://cybilportal.org/publications/>

⁴ European Commission. (n.d.). EU Cybersecurity Observatory. Retrieved March 12, 2025, from <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library>

⁵ World Economic Forum. (n.d.). Centre for Cybersecurity. Retrieved March 12, 2025, from <https://centres.weforum.org/centre-for-cybersecurity/insights>

⁶ European Union Agency for Cybersecurity. (n.d.). ENISA. Retrieved November 10, 2024, from <https://www.enisa.europa.eu/publications>

⁷ DIGITALEUROPE. Retrieved November 10, 2024, from <https://www.digitaleurope.org/resources/>

Platforms, Joint Cybersecurity Training Programs, Integrated Crisis Management Frameworks, Shared Resource Allocation, Harmonised Cybersecurity Framework, Cybersecurity Governance Framework, Public-Private Cybersecurity Partnerships, National Cybersecurity Simulations, Cross-Sector Crisis Management, Create Cybersecurity Innovation Hubs, Launch Joint Cybersecurity R&D Initiatives, Joint Cybersecurity Procurement Programs, Cross-Sector Cybersecurity Workshops, Cybersecurity Awareness Campaigns, Exchange Programs, Collaborative Threat Intelligence Networks, Simplify Technology Transfer Processes, Develop Unified Policy Frameworks, Promote Cross-Sector Policy Dialogue, Streamline Compliance Processes, Leverage International Best Practices, Cultural Exchange Initiatives, Develop Common Terminologies and Protocols, Trust-Building Activities, Fast Reorganisation Programs, Vulnerability and Threat Analysis Policies, Shared Funding and Resources, Long-Term Collaboration Agreements, Unified Threat Intelligence (TI) and Early Warning Systems, Cross-Sector Vulnerability Disclosure Mechanisms.

- Use of data mining software (e.g., ATLAS.ti/NVivo, WORDij or IRaMuTeQ): A semi-automated analysis of text can also help identify relevant quotes, patterns of association between keywords, hierarchical position of clusters (stemmed or aggregated words) or the context where single keywords are used. The selected software also allows the creation of visual representations of results in the form of Tag Clouds and/or histograms.

Criteria for inclusion/exclusion of practices for in-depth review:

Inclusion criteria:

- **Relevance to the topic:** the practice directly addresses cybersecurity challenges in civilian or defence sectors.
- **Effectiveness:** show success in mitigating threats, improving resilience, or enhancing coordination.
- **Scalability:** the practice shows a potential for adaptation across different regions, organisations, or sectors.
- **Collaboration:** encourages cross-sector cooperation between civilian and defence entities.
- **Evidence-based:** a practice is supported by case studies, data, or expert validation, for example.
- **Geographic and temporal settings:** practices will be drawn from EU27 countries and associated countries, focusing on those implemented from 2015 onward.

Exclusion criteria:

- **Limited relevance:** practices that do not specifically address cybersecurity in the civilian or defence sectors will be excluded.

- Unconfirmed effectiveness: practices which lack empirical evidence, case studies, or proven success.
- Applicability: practices that cannot be scaled or adapted beyond a specific use case.
- Redundancy: similar or overlapping practices will be excluded.
- Outdated methods: practices with the use of ineffective cybersecurity approaches will be excluded.
- Geographic and temporal settings: practices from countries outside the EU27 or associated countries, as well as those prior to 2015, will be excluded.

Outcome: An Excel template is created ([D4.1 long list of practices](#)) to organise the practices and their information, including the following columns:

Description	
Objective	
Primary:	Secondary:
Alignment with D2.2. (A.1 – A.32 solutions)	
Implementation Strategy	
Success factors	Challenges
Impact	
Transferability	

Part of [D4.1 long list of practices](#) that is connected to in-depth review (view of a part of the table in Excel):

General information about Best Practices			Criteria for inclusion/exclusion of practices for in-depth review							In-depth review							
Description	Time coverage	Geographic coverage	Relevance to the topic	Effectiveness	Scalability	Collaboration	Evidence-based	Geographic and temporal setting	Inclusion/exclusion from the analysis	Primary objective	Secondary objective	Implementation strategy	Success factors	Challenges	Alignment with EU Policies	Impact	Transferability

5.2.2 Identification of shortlisted practices

Goals and methods: The objective is to establish clear and well-defined selection criteria for identifying "best practices." To ensure a structured and objective evaluation, a Likert scale ranging from Very Low (1) to Very High (5) will be applied. Each practice will be assessed based on these criteria, and those scoring a total of 25–30 points (tentative) or higher will proceed to the next stage.

A total of 20 practices will be shortlisted for further assessment, ensuring a balanced and representative selection of high-quality practices.

Outcome: Each practice will be evaluated in the same Excel template based on the following criteria:

Factor	Description	Rating
Feasibility	This factor assessed the practicality of implementing each best practice based on available resources, regulatory constraints, and technical readiness.	From Very Low (1) to Very High (5), depending on how easily the practice can be implemented.
Impact	This factor measured the potential of the best practice to improve collaboration between the civilian and defence cybersecurity sectors.	From Very Low (1) to Very High (5), based on its measurable effects on response times, information sharing, and strategic alignment.
Efficiency	Evaluates how well the practice delivers high impact with minimal resources.	From Very Low (1) to Very High (5), based on the balance between impact and resource investment.
Scalability	Scalability refers to the potential of each best practice to be expanded or adapted across various EU countries and sectors.	From Very Low (1) to Very High (5), based on how well the practice can be replicated across multiple regions or sectors.
Innovation	This factor measures whether practice introduces new technologies, methodologies, approaches or not.	From Very Low (1) to Very High (5), based on how innovative the practice is in driving dual-use technologies or novel collaboration methods.

Factor	Description	Rating
Risk Mitigation	This factor assessed how well each best practice addresses known cybersecurity risks and mitigates potential challenges.	From Very Low (1) to Very High (5), depending on the extent of risk reduction offered.
Ethical Considerations	Assesses the ethical implications of implementing the best practice, such as privacy concerns and data protection.	From Very Low (1) to Very High (5), based on the risk of ethical violations and potential conflicts with human rights frameworks.
Total points		Max 35 points

To ensure consistency across all evaluations, we will use the following scale:

- **Very Low (1):** The criterion is barely met or not addressed at all.
- **Low (2):** The criterion is addressed, but with significant weaknesses or gaps.
- **Moderate (3):** The criterion is met to an acceptable degree, but with room for improvement.
- **High (4):** The criterion is well met, with only minor areas that could be improved.
- **Very High (5):** The criterion is fully and effectively met, with strong evidence and no notable weaknesses.

This unified approach will help us ensure fairness and comparability across evaluations.

5.2.3 Expert validation and rating

Goals and methods: The 20 shortlisted practices will be shared with identified relevant experts for evaluation. Based on their feedback, the top 11 best practices will be validated and finalised.

Expert selection process: Experts for best practice validation will be selected based on the criteria below. To facilitate the process, experts will be brought into the evaluation through the consortium members' network. A minimum of four experts will be required to ensure the reliability of the evaluation. If any selected experts request remuneration for their contribution, payment may be provided, following the established justification procedures.

Payment Justification: To ensure compliance and accountability in the use of funds, the involvement of paid experts in the validation activities will be properly documented and justified. For reporting and audit purposes, the Direct Offer Collection approach will be followed.

Direct Offer Collection: Experts already known to the consortium will be contacted directly to confirm their availability and the fee they would charge for the activity. Their written offer or confirmation will serve as supporting evidence for the payment.

Additionally, Ambassadors and the Advisory Board will be invited to validate the best practices on a voluntary basis.

Expert selection criteria for Cybersecurity best practice validation: To ensure a rigorous and objective validation process, experts will be selected based on the following criteria:

Criteria	Description	Rating
Relevant expertise	At least five years of experience in cybersecurity, civil defence, or related fields, with knowledge in areas like cyber risk management, policy, threat intelligence, or critical infrastructure protection. Priority experience in collaboration between the civilian and defence sectors.	From Very Low (1) to Very High (5)
Institutional affiliation	Experts should be from national cybersecurity agencies, defence ministries, EU/international bodies (e.g., ENISA, NATO CCDCOE), research institutions, private sector firms, or NGOs involved in cybersecurity.	From Very Low (1) to Very High (5)
Experience in best practice assessment	Prior work in evaluating, developing, or implementing cybersecurity frameworks, standards (e.g., NIS 2), or policy benchmarking.	From Very Low (1) to Very High (5)
Involvement in Cybersecurity initiatives	Participation in EU-funded projects, advisory panels, or cybersecurity research programmes.	From Very Low (1) to Very High (5)
Independence	No conflicts of interest and commitment to an unbiased evaluation process based on predefined criteria	From Very Low (1) to Very High (5)
No conflict of interest	Experts must act impartially, have no conflicts of interest, and commit to an unbiased evaluation process based on predefined criteria.	From Very Low (1) to Very High (5)
Availability	Willingness to review the 20 shortlisted practices, provide structured feedback, and engage in discussions as needed	From Very Low (1) to Very High (5)
Total points		Max 35 points

To ensure consistency across all evaluations, we will use the following scale:

- **Very Low (1):** The criterion is barely met or not addressed at all.
- **Low (2):** The criterion is addressed, but with significant weaknesses or gaps.
- **Moderate (3):** The criterion is met to an acceptable degree, but with room for improvement.

- **High (4):** The criterion is well met, with only minor areas that could be improved.
- **Very High (5):** The criterion is fully and effectively met, with strong evidence and no notable weaknesses.

This unified approach will help us ensure fairness and comparability across evaluations.

Outcome: A dedicated **COcyber consultation event** will be organised to present and evaluate a shortlist of 20 selected best practices. During this event, experts, Ambassadors, and Advisory Board members will assess each practice based on predefined evaluation criteria and KPIs.

Approximately **10 working days before the event**, participants will receive the [D4.1 short list of practices](#), which will include a summary of the 20 best practices and the relevant evaluation criteria. This will allow them to familiarise themselves with the content and prepare for the scoring process.

During the event, participants will be asked to **score each best practice** using predefined rating scales (e.g., 1–5 or low/medium/high impact). The scoring will be conducted live using tools such as [Poll Everywhere](#), [Mentimeter](#), or other suitable digital platforms.

The COcyber consultation will also serve to refine and finalise the evaluation rankings based on group discussions and aggregated results.

To ensure consistency across all evaluations, we will use the following scale:

- **Very Low (1):** The criterion is barely met or not addressed at all.
- **Low (2):** The criterion is addressed, but with significant weaknesses or gaps.
- **Moderate (3):** The criterion is met to an acceptable degree, but with room for improvement.
- **High (4):** The criterion is well met, with only minor areas that could be improved.
- **Very High (5):** The criterion is fully and effectively met, with strong evidence and no notable weaknesses.

The highest-rated 20 practices will be documented and recommended for further implementation and scaling across the EU Member States.

Potential evaluation criteria and KPIs:

Factor	Description	Rating
Collaborative success	Experts will assess the level of information sharing, joint training, and operational coordination among stakeholders. KPI: Number of entities involved in the initiative and the frequency of joint activities or exercises.	From Very Low (1) to Very High (5)

<p>Resource sharing and integration</p>	<p>Experts will measure the extent to which cybersecurity tools, platforms, or infrastructure are shared across entities. KPI: Number of shared cybersecurity assets (e.g., databases, platforms, or tools) among participants.</p>	<p>From Very Low (1) to Very High (5)</p>
<p>Scalability and adaptability</p>	<p>Experts will assess whether the best practice can be easily adapted to different organisational structures, threat landscapes, and national contexts. KPI: Number of successful adaptations in different sectors or countries.</p>	<p>From Very Low (1) to Very High (5)</p>
<p>Sustainability</p>	<p>Evaluates whether the practice has a long-term impact and can be maintained beyond initial funding or support. KPI: Number of participating organisations continuing or planning to continue implementation after project funding ends.</p>	<p>From Very Low (1) to Very High (5)</p>
<p>Innovation and technological advancement</p>	<p>Measures how innovative the practice is, particularly in leveraging emerging technologies (AI, blockchain, quantum security, etc.). KPI: Number of new technological solutions introduced or enhanced by the practice.</p>	<p>From Very Low (1) to Very High (5)</p>
<p>Transferability and knowledge dissemination</p>	<p>Examines how well the practice facilitates knowledge sharing and can be adopted by new stakeholders. KPI: Number of training sessions, workshops, or knowledge-sharing events</p>	<p>From Very Low (1) to Very High (5)</p>

	conducted based on the practice.	
Total points		Max 30 points

To ensure consistency across all evaluations, we will use the following scale:

- **Very Low (1):** The criterion is barely met or not addressed at all.
- **Low (2):** The criterion is addressed, but with significant weaknesses or gaps.
- **Moderate (3):** The criterion is met to an acceptable degree, but with room for improvement.
- **High (4):** The criterion is well met, with only minor areas that could be improved.
- **Very High (5):** The criterion is fully and effectively met, with strong evidence and no notable weaknesses.

This unified approach will help us ensure fairness and comparability across evaluations.

1. Final reporting of Best Practices

Goals and methods: Produce a comprehensive report documenting the methodology, findings, and validated best practices.

Dissemination and Accessibility of Best Practices: To ensure wide accessibility, the selected 11 best practices will be published in two formats:

- A detailed online repository on the project’s website, featuring full case studies, methodology, and supporting documentation.
- A part of a condensed 30–page report (Deliverable D4.1), which will provide a summary of each best practice, including a structured overview, key takeaways, and a direct link to the full online documentation.

Each best practice published in the online repository will follow the [Template of Best Practices](#), ensuring a **consistent structure** that includes key details such as objectives, implementation strategy, success factors, challenges, impact, scalability, etc.

Outcomes: Guidelines on cybersecurity civil-defence cooperation.

The document of up to 30 pages will present the **collection of selected best practices** as well as **cooperation guidelines for cybersecurity civilian and defence spheres actors**.

The report will feature **11 best practices** identified through the evaluation process, providing a structured analysis of their implementation, impact, and scalability. This report will provide detailed information on each best practice, including:

- An overview and context of each best practice, detailing its purpose and the cybersecurity challenges it addresses.
- Implementation details, outlining who was involved and how the initiative was rolled out.
- Effectiveness in mitigating cyber threats and improving civil-defence coordination, showcasing KPIs and other impact metrics.
- Efficiency, cost savings, and resource optimisation, demonstrating measurable improvements in cyber resilience and risk reduction (if applicable).

- Challenges faced and how they were mitigated.
- Scalability—how the best practice can be tailored for different contexts and sectors, supported by real-world examples of successful adaptation.
- Collaborative success, particularly in cross-sector cooperation, joint training, and information sharing.
- Policy alignment and compliance with frameworks like NIS2 (if applicable).
- Sustainability, analysing the practice’s long-term viability beyond initial funding and adoption rates among stakeholders.
- Resilience and incident recovery, detailing how effectively organisations can bounce back from cyber incidents (if applicable).

The **Guidelines on cybersecurity civil-defence cooperation** will provide structured insights and actionable recommendations, based on 11 best practices insights. The report will include the following sections (*tentative*):

1. Introduction
 - Purpose and scope of the guidelines.
 - Importance of cooperation between the cybersecurity and civil-defence sectors.
 - Key objectives and expected outcomes.
2. Best practices
 - Key findings and main conclusions of the 11 Best Practices.
3. Implementation Framework
 - General steps for best practices implementation.
 - Key factors for success.
 - Challenges and strategies for overcoming them.
4. Recommendations and conclusions
 - Recommendations for enhancing cybersecurity cooperation.
 - Strategies for ensuring long-term sustainability and scalability.
 - Next steps for improving EU-wide cybersecurity civil-defence collaboration.

2. Conclusions

Deliverable **D4.1 – Guidelines on Cybersecurity Civil-Defence Cooperation** will build upon the insights gained from the evaluation of **11 best practices**, providing a structured framework for enhancing collaboration between civilian and defence sectors. The forthcoming work will focus on collaborative **success, sustainability, and the scalability** of best practices, exploring how they can be adapted across different organisations, sectors, and EU countries using data from previous successful implementations. These **guidelines will serve as a foundation for future improvements in cybersecurity cooperation across the EU**, ensuring their relevance and applicability in evolving security landscapes. The best practices will be further **used to feed into the T4.2** and be presented at the project’s final conference.

6 Appendix 2

[Practices on the COcyber website](#) (in development with LC)

7 Appendix 3

[COcyber D2.2 Needs Assessment Report](#)